

FOCUS-5: Consent video for protected characteristic data capture during public engagements

Development, co-production, and feedback

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This report summarises the rationale for, and next steps arising from, a short consent animation designed to explain why protected characteristic and demographic data may be requested during public involvement and engagement work, how those data are used, and how they are protected. It sits within a wider effort to make PPIE activity itself more **FAIR: findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable**.

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1. Background and problem context

Patient and Public Involvement and Engagement (PPIE) activity has grown in scale, complexity, and strategic importance across the Health Data space. Organisations are increasingly seeking to collect demographic and protected characteristic data from public contributors to understand who is participating, who may be under-represented, and whether engagement activities are conducted in an inclusive and equitable manner. This is part of efforts to uphold the principles of the Public Sector Equality Duty. While this is appropriate in principle, the explanation provided at the point of data collection is often limited, inconsistent, or absent. This is in part because UK PPIE activity often falls outside formal Research Ethics Committee (REC) review, and as such the rigour regarding demographic monitoring in PPIE has not historically been supported by routine national systems or requirements. This also affects consent arrangements for demographic data capture, which may be less consistently formalised than in conventional research participation, where the consent process must be described in detail to gain REC approvals. Reducing the quality of “informed consent”. (1, 2, 3)

Informed consent is a process through which a person is given relevant information in an understandable form, has the opportunity to consider and ask questions, understands the material facts, and makes a voluntary decision free from coercion, undue influence, or deception. (4)

This work emerged in response to this practical and increasingly visible challenge within Patient and Public Involvement and Engagement regarding the ethical and safe use of data.

This gives rise to two interrelated concerns. First, individuals may be asked to provide sensitive personal information without receiving a sufficiently clear explanation of why it is being collected, how it will be used, and what safeguards govern its handling. Second, where data capture practices vary across teams and organisations, opportunities for comparison, shared learning, gap analysis, and the development of more timely system-level insight are reduced. In practical terms, inconsistency in data collection limits the ability to assess whether public engagement is becoming broader, fairer, and more effective over time.

The then North West Secure Data Environment (SDE) and FOCUS-5 public engagement lead identified a need for improved tools to support real-time data capture and insight generation for public engagement. Exploring this need further at the March 2025 DARE UK Early Adopters launch in Nottingham, collaboration began with the PANORAMA project’s PPIE lead around this shared challenge. From this, a wider package of supporting resources began to emerge to aid the adoption of a more standardised data capture dataset. The consent video formed part of this broader effort, with the specific aim of strengthening transparency at the point of collection by explaining why personal data is requested, how it is used, and how a more coordinated approach to data capture, storage and analysis could enhance insight generation, consistency, and organisational learning.

Within the wider DARE UK context, this issue is significant due to its implications for communication practice, as well as for broader questions of trustworthiness, public benefit, interoperability, and the development of practical standards that can operate across organisational boundaries. A consent video may appear modest as a discrete output though it forms part of a process that sits at the intersection of public trust and operational consistency. Improving this process can enhance the inclusivity of the evidence base generated from aggregated PPIE activity and data capture across multiple geographies and organisations. Particularly when paired with near-real-time data visualisation tools that should sit atop such structured data. This is described in further detail here: <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18266247>.

2. Purpose of the video

The purpose of the video was therefore not simply to obtain permission in a transactional sense. It was to provide a clearer, more honest explanation of why these data are requested in the first place. In plain terms, the video is intended to help public participants understand that protected characteristic and demographic data can support fairer engagement, better reporting, better planning, and more credible accountability.

The video was also designed to support greater consistency across settings. A reusable, organisation-agnostic explanation offers a route towards more unified data capture processes, while avoiding each team reinventing the wheel or producing explanations of mixed quality. That is especially useful in a landscape where PPIE is increasingly expected to support shared learning across programmes, regions, and infrastructures rather than remaining locked within local narrative reports.

A further purpose was transparency. If we want people to trust us with sensitive information, we need to explain not only the hoped for utility, but also the boundaries. That includes voluntariness, proportionality, the distinction between identifiable and de-identified information, and the fact that data capture should support inclusion and insight whilst reducing the risk of appearing to data-mine.

3. Approach

This work used an iterative co-design and prototype testing approach, bringing together PPIE professionals and public contributors to develop, review and refine a consent resource for engagement data capture. The method combined rapid-cycle drafting with staged feedback from both involved and independent public advisory groups, allowing early assumptions about clarity, accessibility, trust and data protection reassurance to be tested with intended audiences before professional production. The process was therefore both developmental and evaluative, using feedback to improve the resource while also documenting wider learning about consent communication in PPIE insight generation.

May 2025: first draft video produced

- Joint meetings between FOCUS-5 and PANORAMA PPIE professionals covering the three northern SDEs of the North West, Yorkshire Humber, and North East and North Cumbria started to jointly coordinate efforts around the challenge of PPIE insight production.
- This resulted in the identification of a consent for data capture process as part of addressing governance challenges and requirements proactively.
- A first-draft consent video combining knowledge on informed consent processes, data capture, management, and use was generated in a short sprint. This emphasised why this matters, how it helps with improving PPIE delivery, principles of safe data management, and the voluntary nature of consent, which does not affect rights to participate. This involved the production of a 3-minute script, to which an AI voice-over was generated as a placeholder for professional voice actors and pairing timed animations to support comprehension and engagement.

May and June 2025: video feedback sessions

- Feedback was gathered from the LSC Data into Impact Programme Public Advisory Group which included six members as an online semi-structured discussion.
 - Revisions and updates were implemented.

June 18th: PEDRI Frontiers Meeting

- Public Insights Tool and Consent video poster presentation at stakeholder event.

September 2025: video feedback session (Appendix 1)

- A structured evaluation session from North East and North Cumbria Public Advisory Group (PAAG) was then delivered with a group unconnected to the work or the developer. This provided more diverse perspectives and a fresh set of eyes from audience members not yet familiar with the PPIE leads work.
- Six members of the North East and North Cumbria PAAG provided the video in advance with stimulus questions and joined a 1-hour facilitated session.
- Feedback was collected from everyone in the call, including one written submission from a participant who could not join online.
- The comments focus on clarity, accessibility, visual design, audio delivery, engagement, and reassurance about data protection.

Next steps

- Integrate feedback into a final format and commission a professional creation of the video.
 - Pre-production ready draft video located here: [10.5281/zenodo.19369059](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19369059)

4. Feedback and evaluation summary

Lancashire and South Cumbria Public Advisory Group inputs (May and June 2025)

Feedback was broadly positive. Members felt the video was clear, about the right length, and used effective graphics. It explained well why data is collected and, importantly, made clear that people can choose not to share their personal information.

Key accessibility feedback was that subtitles or captions are essential. Future improvements could include additional languages and a signed version. Members also wanted a real human voice, not AI, with a slightly slower pace, regional accents, and direct, inclusive language such as “you”, “us”, and “our”.

Content suggestions included briefly explaining what “data” means and being clearer about the benefits of collecting it. Feedback also supported the wider design approach, which has been shaped by public concerns around consent, privacy, understanding, and choice, alongside principles such as the Five Safes, PEDRI values, transparency, and data literacy. Further refinements included avoiding red because of political connotations and writing out “General Data Protection Regulation” in full.

Figure 1 - Summary slide of feedback from Lancashire and South Cumbria Public Advisory Group

North East and North Cumbria Public Advisory Group (September 2025)

Version one of the animation was reviewed with public contributors from the North East and North Cumbria SDE public group, alongside additional written feedback. The broad message from that session was encouraging. Reviewers felt the video had a clear intent, looked professional, and communicated the core idea well.

The feedback also showed clearly where refinement is needed. The opening was felt to be too dense and slightly top-heavy, with too much information arriving too quickly. Reviewers wanted the purpose stated

more explicitly within the first few seconds. They also wanted the content broken into more digestible chunks so the flow felt easier to follow.

Pacing, narration, and accessibility were recurring themes. The AI voice was perceived by some as too fast and a little impersonal. Suggestions included a warmer and more natural voice, better pauses, subtitling, audio description, and more attention to the needs of neurodiverse audiences and people with visual or sensory impairments. Visual choices also mattered. Participants highlighted that some transitions were too rapid, some imagery felt distracting, and some slides contained more information than viewers could comfortably process in the time available.

There were also important content-level points. Reviewers wanted clearer reassurance that participation is voluntary, that data collection does not affect access to opportunities or services, and that legal and governance protections exist without turning the video into a technical lecture. They also encouraged us to use more precise wording, particularly moving away from “anonymous” where “de-identified” is more accurate.

5. Why this matters beyond one video

Although this report is about a single communication product, the issue is wider. Better explanation at the point of capture supports better quality data, but it also supports more ethical practice. If people understand why information is requested, are free to decline, and can see the public value clearly, then data collection becomes more legitimate and more useful.

This links directly to the wider ambition of treating PPIE itself as part of our transparency infrastructure. If we want to understand whether engagement is inclusive, whether underrepresented communities are missing, whether concerns are shifting over time, and whether cross-organisational work is becoming more coherent, then our own engagement data needs to be captured in ways that are understandable, proportionate, and reusable. It is part of the enabling architecture required for more mature and FAIR public engagement practice. PPIE that is itself findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable. By normalising coproduced structured data capture processes, we can build data visualisation and insight production tools without further data cleaning and wrangling. This can lead to real-time insights generation that can improve resource allocation and strategy to deliver more equitable engagement across the UK and the health data space.

6. Action and next steps

The next phase should focus on turning version one into a more robust and reusable resource. The key actions are set out below.

- Integrate the evaluation feedback into the final script and storyboard, especially around clarity of purpose, chunking of content, pacing, precision of language, and reassurance about voluntariness and protection.
- Replace the current narration approach with a human voice, or a more human-sounding voice at a minimum, with deliberate pacing, pauses, subtitles, and accessibility-conscious design choices built in from the start rather than added on later.
- Professionally animate the final product so the visual quality matches the seriousness of the topic, while avoiding unnecessary complexity, rapid transitions, or imagery that distracts from the core message.
- Develop an organisation-agnostic short version focused on the core principles of data capture only, suitable for reuse across programmes and settings where protected characteristic or demographic data are collected during PPIE activity.
- Develop a longer companion version that places the same explanation within a wider health data research context, including Five Safes framing and a clearer account of how data use, governance, and public benefit connect.
- Consider the video as part of a suite rather than a one-off asset, with scope for linked easy read, storyboard, subtitle first, audio described, and other accessible formats, so the communication model itself reflects the inclusion we are trying to evidence.

7. Closing reflection

This work has always been about more than a media product. It is about setting a better standard for how we ask for sensitive information within public involvement work. If we want stronger evidence, better interoperability, and more credible transparency, then we need to improve the small operational moments where trust is either built or quietly lost. This video may represent one of those moments.

Connected research infrastructure requires connected trust infrastructure, too. A clearer, reusable, public-facing explanation of protected characteristic data capture is a practical contribution to that agenda and a sensible next step in making PPIE activity more comparable across the system.

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The FOCUS-5 project was funded as part of the UKRI DARE UK – Phase 2 (UKRI Data and Analytics Research Environments UK- Phase 2) programme. DARE UK Phase 2 is funded by the UKRI Digital Research Infrastructure Programme; and Phase 2 is delivered jointly by HDR UK, and ADR UK, and funded by UKRI Digital Research Infrastructure Fund.

Thanks to the members of the Lancashire and South Cumbria Data into Impact Programme Public Advisory and Accountability Group (lscsde.org) for feedback and development support.

Thanks to the members of the North East and Northumbria Public Advisory Group

Thanks to the PANORAMA project for supporting engagement activities to improve coproduction and ideation. PANORAMA was funded as part of the UKRI DARE UK – Phase 2 (UKRI Data and Analytics Research Environments UK- Phase 2) programme.

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10. Appendix 1: Copy of Report Key Themes and Feedback

This appendix outlines the feedback from North East North Cumbria Public Advisory Groups supported by the PANORAMA project. This was authored by Kathryn Brennan (now Kathryn Eden)

Summary of feedback

Overall, the video clearly shared the main messages and was visually appealing. However, some areas could be improved, such as pacing, amount of information, slide order, and accessibility.

Positive points from most reviewers:

- The video was clear and easy to understand.
- The visuals were engaging and professional.
- The key messages were well explained.

Areas that could be improved:

- Some parts were too fast, making it hard to follow.
- Slides had too much information; simpler slides would be better.
- Some visuals and wording may be hard for certain audiences to follow.
- The order of some slides was confusing.
- The AI voice could be improved by making it warmer, a mix of male and female voices or a more regional accent.

10.1. Key themes explored:

10.1.1. Clarity of Purpose

- Participants appreciated the overall explanation of why data is collected but suggested that the introduction should clearly state the purpose within the first few seconds.
- The first 10 seconds were noted as particularly dense, with too much “top-heavy” data, potentially overwhelming or disengaging viewers.
- It was recommended that the video explicitly address the target audience (research participants and public engagement professionals) to avoid ambiguity.
- The structure of the video could benefit from clear “chunks” or sections (e.g., purpose, type of data collected, data protection measures) to help viewers process the information more effectively.
- Some participants found the sequencing confusing—for example, showing a world map followed by a UK map. Using consistent geographical context early on (starting with the UK) was suggested.

10.1.2. Audio and Narration

- Several participants found the AI-generated voice too fast, especially toward the end of sections, giving the impression of “rushing” through content. Suggestions included slowing down the narration, adding pauses, and using a warmer, calmer, or more relatable voice.
- There was a recommendation to include a mix of male and female voices for inclusivity.

- Pauses would also help incorporate accessibility features like audio descriptions for visually impaired viewers and subtitles for deaf or hard-of-hearing audiences.
- It was recommended to keep audio descriptions concise to avoid disrupting the main narration.

10.1.3. Visual Design

- The black opening screen and rapidly changing images confused some viewers. Alternative backgrounds (eg, light blue) and more consistent imagery were suggested to improve readability and accessibility.
- Some elements, such as the “counting hands” slide, rockets, or segregated wheelchair icons, were noted as potentially distracting or misrepresenting inclusion.
- Visual transitions should be smoothed to avoid rapid flashes that could trigger photosensitive viewers.

10.1.4. Content and Messaging

- Participants emphasised the importance of balancing detail and brevity. While the video should be informative, too many rapidly changing visuals or dense slides make it harder to follow.
- Clarifying terms such as “anonymous” vs. “de-identified” was recommended to ensure accuracy.
- Feedback suggested emphasising that participation is voluntary and data collection will not impact access to services or engagement opportunities.
- Some participants requested concise reassurances about legal compliance (eg, There are lots of laws to keep your data safe. This project follows all of them.) and secure data storage without overloading viewers with technical details.

10.1.5. Accessibility and Inclusion

- Attention to colour contrast, background consistency, and readability was highlighted as crucial for neurodiverse and dyslexic audiences.
- Consideration for diverse audiences, including people with epilepsy, dementia, or other sensory sensitivities, was advised when designing animations and transitions.
- Suggestions were made to provide audio descriptions, subtitling, and thoughtful visual pacing to ensure content is accessible to all participants.
- Participants highlighted the need to avoid aiming visuals too low or overly simplistic, which could be perceived as insulting to a broader audience.

10.2. Recommendations for Next Steps

10.2.1. Revise Introduction

- Clearly state purpose, audience, and key message in the first few seconds.
- Use a concise “call to action” at the end.

10.2.2. Improve Audio Delivery

- Slow down narration and add pauses.
- Explore more natural or human-like voices.
- Incorporate audio description and subtitling.

10.2.3. Refine Visuals

- Standardise background and colour palette for accessibility.
- Remove or adjust potentially distracting elements (eg, rockets, counting hands).
- Ensure inclusive representation in images.
- Reduce slide density and simplify visual content to improve clarity.

10.2.4. Clarify Content and Terminology

- Replace “anonymous” with “de-identified” where appropriate.
- Reinforce voluntary participation and legal compliance.
- Simplify complex information into digestible segments.

10.2.5. Accessibility Considerations

- Test animations for visual sensitivity issues.
- Provide clear text alternatives and readable fonts for all slides.
- Ensure pacing allows neurodiverse participants to absorb information.

10.3. Conclusion

The animation successfully communicates the principles of data collection during public engagement but requires refinements in clarity, accessibility, narration, and visual design.

Implementing these changes will improve comprehension, inclusivity, and trust among participants, ultimately supporting more effective and ethical public engagement.

Acknowledgements

The animation was produced by Lancashire Hospitals NHS Foundation Trust as part of the FOCUS-5 DARE UK project.